

Exploring companies' domains of responsibility and level of importance: the consumers' perspective of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Abstract

Since consumers' perspective regarding Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities can be different from that of the companies, we thus empirically test consumers' evaluations of different CSR activities and their relative importance through consumer loyalty towards a company. In particular, the study focused on companies' CSR activities in energy facility development (geothermal energy) to carry out a questionnaire survey among around 1500 consumers located in BRICS capital cities – i.e. Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa. By adopting the rologit model, the study highlighted that CSR activities considering the impact of companies' operations on local communities had the highest relative importance for consumers. Companies can also gain strategic advantages when performing CSR activities that avoid impacts on the environment and ensure reliable communications. This study contributes to the literature on CSR-consumer binomial by taking the perspective of consumers in evaluating different areas of responsibility of CSR and related activities.

Keywords

Sustainability, Corporate social responsibility (CSR), cross-cultural differences, companies' CSR domains, consumer behaviour, consumer loyalty

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1. Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been variously conceptualized in the literature, reflecting the degree and domains of responsibility that can be ascribed to companies (Lee et al., 2012; Hemphill, 1997). Three domains have emerged as essential building blocks for effective CSR strategies and activities. Companies primarily demonstrate their CSR efforts to their stakeholders through the social and environmental domains (Ali et al., 2017). In addition, a third essential domain of responsibility refers to CSR communication strategies and activities, since literature has highlighted stakeholders' lack of information and recognition of relevant CSR activities (Lee et al., 2012; Swaen & Chumpitaz, 2008).

Most studies of CSR take an organizational level of analysis (Anbarasan, 2018), including – among other – examining the rationale for motivating companies to engage in CSR and the type of activities adopted (Basu & Palazzo, 2008; Öberseder et al., 2013). However, recent research has focused on CSR as being part of a company's relationships with one of its primary stakeholders, the consumers (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019; Govindan et al., 2014), and in particular on the link between CSR and consumers' responses (Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006; Brunk, 2010). This trend reflects the need for companies to better control the consequences deriving from their CSR activities (Dobers & Halme, 2009), thus enabling them to adequately plan and implement CSR strategies and activities.

Research has supported the beneficial effect of CSR on consumers' responses, such as their satisfaction, and loyalty (Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001; Huang & Cheng, 2016). In particular, consumer loyalty is a commonly used dependent variables in conceptual models aimed at investigating the effect of CSR (Lee et al, 2012), due to its connection with competitiveness: the more a consumer is loyal to a company, the more the company will be likely to achieve good financial performance.

Despite the important role of CSR in determining consumers' responses, CSR domains have been often studied in an aggregated form, and thus little is known about how “[specific] corporate [CSR-related] decisions are perceived by the public” (Brunk, 2010). Consumers' views of these domains should not be substituted by those of companies, as the business perspective regarding the implementation of CSR activities may be different from that of consumers (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019; Brunk, 2010; Galavielle, 2004). For example, companies may communicate their CSR activities by using mass media such as TV and the Internet, while consumers may prefer to receive word-of-mouth (WOM) information from the beneficiaries of such activities, as a sign of the commitment and effective behaviour of the companies. In addition, many companies appear to focus on standard CSR activities and/or domains regardless of the situation and the stakeholders they are dealing with (Lee et al., 2012). This leads to the adoption of the “department store” approach for CSR strategies and activities, which may negatively sharpen companies' and consumers' differences regarding CSR. These differences may reduce the effectiveness of CSR activities and lead to negative consumer responses (Brunk, 2010). Consumer loyalty may then be undermined and the companies' profits may be adversely affected.

This study complements the literature by investigating which CSR-related decisions and associated CSR domains are the most effective in influencing consumers' behaviour. The first aim of the study is to empirically test the CSR domains that consumers value most when deciding whether a company deserves their continued loyalty or not. The second aim is to empirically test the relative importance consumers give to each CSR domain when evaluating their level of loyalty towards a company. Such

aims are pursued by using CSR activities based on real-life approximated situations, since consumers' perceptions of CSR do not necessarily coincide with the actual companies' social performance (Perrini et al., 2010; Bhattacharya et al., 2009). We analyse these evaluations in the five developing countries of Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa (BRICS), using a renewable energy facility development as the setting. By directing our empirical investigations towards developing countries, we fill a gap in the scientific literature, as previously the relationship between CSR and consumers in developed countries has been the focus of analysis (Dobers & Halme, 2009; Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019). The construction of energy facilities represents a meaningful setting, due to its potentially negative impacts on the neighbouring social and natural environments. For this reason, companies causing, for example, extensive environmental damage may experience significant business costs if they do not implement appropriate CSR strategies and activities (Hall et al., 2015).

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the literature concerning the main CSR dimensions and their expected relations with consumers' perceptions. Section 3 describes the data collection and estimation methods. Section 4 presents the statistical results, which are discussed in Section 5, and managerial implications are suggested in Section 6.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 CSR principles and companies' CSR domains

The European Commission defines CSR as “a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis” (European Commission, 2001). Similarly, Savitz and Weber (2006) underlined the importance of the protection of the environment, which should be pursued simultaneously with improvements to the quality of life, without undermining a company's ability to remunerate shareholders. In addition to their economic ones, the responsibilities companies are expected to assume by adopting CSR principles must therefore include responsibilities towards the social and natural environment (Anbarasan, 2018). The area of CSR dealing with social responsibilities – i.e. social CSR domain – generally refers to the establishment of responsible relationships and behaviours with actors such as employees, suppliers, local communities, NGOs, etc., to account for the impact companies have on society. The area of CSR dealing with environmental responsibilities – i.e. environmental CSR domain – includes the establishment of responsible behaviours in terms of environmental protection and the relationships with environmental bodies, to account for the impact companies have on the environment.

The identification of ad-hoc CSR efforts within these domains can represent a source of competitive advantage especially for multinational companies (Jabbour et al., 2015; Xie et al., 2017), since research has highlighted differences in how consumers in developing and developed countries expect companies to fulfil their responsibilities (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019; Brunk, 2010). Particular CSR activities may provoke different reactions from consumers depending on their country of origin, and different levels of importance may be attributed to the same CSR domain, “since the same corporate behaviour which [consumers consider] acceptable in one place may not be accepted in another” (Ali et al., 2017). Thus, a more precise understanding of how consumers see companies' CSR efforts across these domains is required, to effectively explain and predict the outcomes of such efforts

(Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Su et al., 2017). This lack has also been recognized in literature, where studies have highlighted the importance of considering the consumers' perspective when analysing the impact and the effectiveness of companies' CSR efforts (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019; Su et al., 2017), particularly in the context of developing countries which few studies have addressed (Dobers & Halme, 2009; Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019).

In addition to the social and environmental CSR domains, the communication domain is also examined in this study, as communication can positively influence consumer outcome variables. CSR communication is "designed and distributed by the company itself about its CSR efforts" (Morsing 2006; p.171), and aims at informing stakeholders about companies' promises of compliance and excellence regarding their CSR efforts (Parguel et al., 2011). Companies skilled at communicating can better foster consumers' awareness about their CSR efforts and underline the relevance of a specific domain (Perrini et al., 2010; Dobele et al., 2014). However, such communication is often not sufficient. A general lack of knowledge has been identified regarding companies' CSR activities within the social and environmental domains (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019), particularly when considering their recognition from consumers (Perrini et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2012). Thus, the establishment of the communication feature that consumers value the most is essential for companies. This is even truer if acknowledging that consumers are often doubtful about the real nature of CSR efforts (De Vries et al., 2015). In fact, companies can behave opportunistically and make "a selective disclosure of only positive information about [their] performance", deflecting "attention from [their] environmental and social shortcomings" (Vollero et al., 2016). Through being aware of such phenomenon – known as greenwashing –, consumers seek communicational features such as reliability and transparency of information (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019; Hansen et al., 2010), so they can better understand if a company's CSR efforts are sincere. If they detect greenwashing, consumers perceive a lack of sincerity and orient their behaviour towards negative reactions, such as taking part in public protests and changing their purchasing behaviour in favour of other companies (Brunk, 2010). Thus, the way in which companies communicate their CSR efforts – the communicational features they adopt to convey their CSR engagement – also becomes crucial to be evaluated by consumers, in order to explain and predict the outcomes of the CSR efforts.

2.2 Linking CSR and companies' CSR domains with consumer loyalty

Research has supported the beneficial effect of CSR on a variety of consumers' responses. For example, it has an effect on corporate reputation, via both direct and indirect paths (Su et al., 2017; Hsu, 2012), and on consumer-corporate identification, which has often been used as a mediating variable for studying other consumers' responses variables (Huang & Cheng, 2016; Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001). In particular, it has also an effect on consumer loyalty (Perrini et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2012), which refers to a repeat purchase/use of a product or service over a period of time. Consumer loyalty can also be linked to positive WOM, which relates to the consumers' willingness to recommend a product/service to other people or to other consumers in general due to the benefits – emotional, practical, etc. – associated with its usage. The CSR effect on consumer loyalty and WOM is particularly important for companies in order to survive and prosper within highly competitive market environments (Xie et al., 2017; Govindan et al., 2014), in which competition is mainly based on cost-effectiveness.

Despite the aforementioned literature, previous researches have usually analysed CSR as a perceptual construct, relying on an accurate level of consumers' awareness for its assessment (Perrini et al., 2010). Even though consumers are found to be able to recognize the complexity of the concept of CSR and discriminate among its relevant domains (Alvarado-Herrera et al., 2017; Öberseder et al., 2013), evidences suggest that their actual degree of knowledge of companies' CSR activities is usually low (Perrini et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2012). For this reason, studies such as the one of Bhattacharya et al. (2009) affirm the need to use objective measures of companies' CSR activities, in order to better assess how different CSR domains and activities influence consumer responses regardless of their actual degree of knowledge.

Focussing on the present study, we can expect that consumers will acknowledge and consider differently companies' efforts in different CSR domains, and will convert such efforts into a significant degree of loyalty when evaluating them as positive and important. Therefore, we hypothesize that

- 1a) The more a consumer considers the social domain (SD) of a company's CSR activities as positive and important for himself/herself, the more he/she will be prone to be loyal to the company.*
- 1b) The more a consumer considers the environmental domain (ED) of a company's CSR activities as positive and important for himself/herself, the more he/she will be prone to be loyal to the company.*
- 1c) The more a consumer considers the communication domain (CD) of a company's CSR activities as positive and important for himself/herself, the more he/she will be prone to be loyal to the company.*

Some studies have investigated the multidimensional nature of CSR (Maignan, 2001; Alvarado-Herrera et al., 2017). However, very few have attempted to develop a multidimensional scale of measurement by establishing the CSR domains relevant to consumers (Alvarado-Herrera et al., 2017; Öberseder et al., 2014). Öberseder et al. (2013) and Brunk (2010) qualitatively demonstrated that consumers and companies attach a different level of importance to CSR domains and to different aspects within a domain. While consumers consider the ED as of primary importance, companies are less inclined to evaluate environmental concerns as being the highest priority. In terms of the SD, companies are more concerned about their employees' needs whereas consumers tend to give more importance to the effects of the companies' actions on local communities. Reliable and transparent communication is generally considered to be less important by companies than by consumers, but consumers tend to only rely on communication to a limited extent, as they typically find that "promoting CSR is not an indication that a company truly engages in CSR" (Öberseder et al., 2013). Therefore, we hypothesize that:

- 2) The more a company engages in CSR activities following a descending level of importance among the environmental, social and communication domain, the more a consumer will be loyal to the company.*

3. Method

3.1 BRICS countries and the energy sector – geothermal energy

An experimental field study was conducted to empirically test the aforementioned hypotheses. The BRICS developing countries – i.e. Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa – were considered, as they are all emerging economies with similar patterns of development (Cowan et al., 2014). To analyse the relationship between CSR and consumers in BRICS, we focused on companies from the energy sector. This sector is often linked to high environmental and social impacts, and companies within it typically receive more public attention regarding their behaviour (Dobele et al., 2014). Consequently, they are usually more prone to engage in CSR strategies and activities, making consumers more familiar with processing information about their level of social and environmental responsibility. In addition, the development of the energy sector is usually characterized by a trade-off between consumers' service desirability and the impact of energy production. Even though companies should minimize the impacts an energy facility may have on social and natural environments during its construction and running, they usually prioritize urban consumers' energy needs over the protection of these environments at the site of the energy facility, favouring cost-effectiveness. As economic growth in BRICS countries is highly dependent on non-renewable sources (Cowan et al., 2014), companies in this sector should invest in renewable energy infrastructures, to account for the growing energy demand within urban areas without negatively impacting the environment and society, both on the site of the energy facility and more broadly (Cowan et al., 2014). We selected a geothermal energy facility development due to the particular characteristics of this energy source. Geothermal energy is a programmable type of renewable energy, as it is not affected by weather conditions like solar and wind energy. Despite this advantage, the development of geothermal energy has often been impaired by issues related to the above-mentioned trade-off, which has sometimes resulted in local conflicts that have hindered the development of these facilities.

3.2 Sample and survey design

Primary data from a survey conducted among consumers in the metropolitan area of the capital city of each of the BRICS nations were studied. The survey targeted consumers who were either owners of a house or had an electricity bill in their names. This therefore included typical features of the relationship between the consumer and the energy provider and thus met the aims of the survey. Data were collected between January and February 2018. The answers were gathered through computer-assisted web interviews, via the specialist survey collecting company Survey Sampling International (SSI). The sample consisted of approximately 300 respondents per country, giving a total of 1516. The sample included 739 men (48.7% of the total respondents) and 777 women (51.3%).

The rank-ordered logistic regression (rologit) model was chosen to test our hypotheses, which as a vignette-based method has several advantages over questions-based methods. Such method can convey greater realism to the respondent, because it offers “a range of situational or contextual factors that approximate real-life decision-making situations” (Hyman & Steiner, 1996). Thus, the rologit model enables an analysis of “how decision makers combine attributes of alternatives into overall evaluations of the attractiveness of these alternatives” (StataCorp., 2005). The alternatives – or vignettes – represent scenarios that an individual needs to evaluate and rank, while maximizing his/her utility. Within each vignette the individual is presented with different attributes and is asked to provide

an overall evaluation of them. Through the individual's ranking, which represents the dependent variable, the model gives the relative importance that individuals assign to each attribute.

The survey was designed and conducted through four steps: i) identification of the *attributes*; ii) definition of the *modalities of variation* of each attribute; iii) construction of the *vignettes*; and iv) measurement of *preferences*.

- i) We reviewed the current literature and identified three domains related to the CSR concept: the social domain (SD), the environmental domain (ED), and the communication domain (CD). SD was structured using two attributes: the impact of the geothermal development on local communities (ILC) and the nationality of companies' managers involved in the development (MN). The types of stakeholders typically involved in a geothermal energy facility development, i.e., local communities (LCs) (Pellizzone et al., 2017) and managers (Ms) (Ozuem et al., 2016), motivated this choice. The ED was structured using one attribute: potential environmental impact of the geothermal development (EI). Last, the communication domain was structured using one attribute: the transparency of the CSR communication (CUT).
- ii) After identifying the attributes, we established their most relevant modalities of variation. The modalities of variation represent the degrees of variation of an attribute and, as they vary along a broad spectrum of possible degrees, the relative importance given by consumers to each of them can be identified. We referred to the literature to identify an initial list of modalities of variation and their related importance (Öberseder et al., 2014, Öberseder et al., 2013; Brunk, 2010; Ballesteros et al, 2015), and conducted a pre-test with approximately 20 consumers per each BRICS country, asking them to elicit the most appropriate modalities of variation and assign them weights. In fact, to run the rologit model, different weights must be attributed to each modality of variation, to establish the relative importance along the spectrum of possible degrees.
- iii) As the study was conducted in BRICS, we needed to account for lexical/grammatical and interpretational differences. To such aims, a three-steps vignette-building process was carried out which included: i) a translating process following double-translation principles, to ensure translation accuracy (i.e. lexical/grammatical accuracy); ii) a first pre-test to verify the most plausible combinations of the different modalities of variations, and account for interpretational differences between countries; iii) a second pre-test to validate the process of vignette building. At the end, six vignettes were built and the survey was distributed to all of the respondents from BRICS. The vignettes used in the survey are reported in Annex 1.
- iv) The preferences were measured using the individuals' rankings. We asked respondents to follow the sequential choice process. First, they were asked to rank their most preferred vignette out of the six as the first. They were then asked to choose their least preferred vignette out of the remaining five and rank it as the sixth. This process was repeated for the remaining (four) vignettes, identifying the second and the fifth, and the third and the fourth. This process is known as the "repeated best-worst", and can help respondents rank their preferences (González Dávila et al., 2017).

The survey was structured into three sections: 1) an introduction regarding the aim of the study, the institution and the researchers involved, and the time needed to fulfil the questionnaire; 2) context information about the vignettes and their rankings; 3) participants' demographic information i.e., gender, age and level of study. Before the ranking, the respondents were provided with context information about the vignettes they were about to evaluate, as this can facilitate semantic processes (Shapiro, 1999). To account for additional bias, the introduction ensured the anonymity and

confidentiality of the respondents, and requested that they responded as truthfully as possible because there were no right or wrong answers. Each respondent was assured about the use of aggregated data and the scientific, non-commercial and non-promotional objectives of the study. Missing values within the ranking implied the exclusion of the respondent from the study. Table 1 displays attributes, modalities of variation and associated weights.

Table 1

Table 1. Attributes, modalities of variation and associated weights

3.3 Empirical model

The rank-ordered logistic regression model “can be generated through a random utility model where respondents rank the m alternatives” or vignettes (Guimarães et al., 2016) (in this study $m = 6$), in accordance with their preferences – in our case with their willingness to keep purchasing electricity from the same provider. The utility obtained from alternative $j = 1, \dots, m$ is given by

$$U_j = \beta_{0,j} + \beta_{1,j}X_1 + \dots + \beta_{k,j}X_k + \varepsilon_k$$

where

- $X_1 \dots X_k$ are the explanatory variables, i.e., the modalities of variation of the attributes ILC, MN, EI and CUT;
- $\beta_{0,j}, \beta_{1,j} \dots \beta_{k,j}$ represent the coefficients to be estimated by the statistical software (Stata);
- ε_k represents the errors terms.

Any ranking of the m vignettes can be seen as a sequence of company actions, ranging from those with the highest individual utility – in terms of consumer loyalty – to those with the lowest utility (Guimarães et al., 2016).

Table 2

Table 2. Hypotheses with the hypothesized paths and signs (Source: authors)

4. Results

When all BRICS countries are considered (Tab. 3), the results show that all attributes are significant. In addition, ILC, EI and CUT have positive coefficients, while MN has a negative coefficient. Consequently, H1b and H1c are confirmed, while H1a is confirmed for ILC but not for MN.

When considering the strength of the coefficients in the case of all BRICS, ILC plays by far the most important role in consumer loyalty towards the company, followed by CUT, EI and MN, respectively. Thus, H2 is not confirmed.

Table 3

Table 3. Coefficients and level of significance for each attribute detailed for all BRICS [*p<0.05 e **p<0.01] (Source: authors).

When examining each country separately (Tab. 4), differences emerged. The level of significance of the attributes EI and CUT changed among the countries, with EI being significant only in the case of China and CUT being not significant only in the case of India. Conversely, ILC and MN do not change among countries, with the former remaining always significant and the latter always not significant. In terms of sign, all the significant coefficients among the countries are positive, implying a positive contribution of such attributes to consumer loyalty towards the company – although with different weights. Consequently, H1a is confirmed for ILC but not for MN, regardless of the country considered. H1b is confirmed only in the case of China, and H1c is confirmed in the cases of Brazil, Russia, China and South Africa.

In terms of coefficient strength, ILC still plays the most important role in consumer loyalty, regardless of the countries considered. Similar to the case of all BRICS countries, the second most important attribute is CUT for three countries out of the five: Brazil, Russia and South Africa. Conversely, CUT is preceded by ENV as the second most important attribute in the case of China. Thus, H2 is not confirmed for any of the countries considered.

Table 4

Table 4. Coefficients and level of significance for each attribute detailed for each country [*p<0.05 e **p<0.01] (Source: authors).

5. Discussion

The findings of this analysis reveal which CSR domains are the most effective in influencing consumers' behaviour, across different cultural environments. In particular, they highlight the type of company CSR activities that can evoke consumers' approval/disapproval, thus affecting their loyalty towards the company.

When considering all BRICS countries, the effect of the companies' behaviour on the well-being of local communities represents the most important attribute influencing whether consumers are loyal or not to the companies. That is, consumers consider of primary importance how and to what extent the development of energy facilities – often questioned about their impacts such as geothermal energy facilities – affect the social environment – i.e. the local communities – nearby such facilities. Previous studies have highlighted the importance of involving local communities when developing energy facilities (Benites-Lazaro & Mello-Thery, 2017; Hall et al., 2015). Our results demonstrate that such involvement can not only determine positive site-specific consequences, such as reducing local tensions between companies and consumers and the absence of boycotts during the building process, but it can also directly and positively affect companies' financial performance.

Unlike ILC, managers' multiculturalism (MN) has little influence on whether consumers are loyal or not to the company. The negative sign also suggests that consumers evaluate more positively the

employment of local than foreign managers, pushing companies to be more bound to their home country and economy. That is, consumers evaluate more positively companies that are prone to share the benefits of their activities within their home country, ensuring the employment of non-foreign managers. However, contrasting behaviour of consumers can be found in the literature. As an example, some studies report that employment is one of the most important concerns for consumers (Crowe & Simon, 2000; Brunks, 2010), while others highlight consumers' lower priority of concerns such as working conditions and human exploitation (Carrigan & Attalia, 2001; Brunks, 2010). Consumer-specific characteristics and the industry under investigation, may explain such contrasting behaviours. Demographic characteristics and cultural aspects can influence behaviour to the extent that they may lead to unique ways of understanding and interpreting facts and events, influencing – sometimes in a contradictory way – CSR-related relationships (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2017). Different industry-specific characteristics may also influence consumer evaluations. For example, the energy sector is often viewed by consumers as a “dirty sector” due to its social and environmental impacts, with a more urgent need for companies to be socially responsible compared with those in different sectors.

Similar to MN, environmental protection is not an important factor influencing whether consumers are loyal or not to the companies in any of the BRICS countries. This contrasts with previous research suggesting that consumers are well aware of the importance of protecting the environment and are even willing to boycott companies that cause environmental damage (Brunks, 2010). In addition, a trade-off emerged from consumers' prioritization of attributes. Local communities' well-being was rated by consumers as the most relevant attribute when they decide to be loyal towards the company, but they evaluated environmental pollution, a potentially direct cause of poor health for local communities, as of little importance. Consumers appear to mentally categorize the actions of companies based on what happens locally, i.e., within the capital city of their home country, or far away from them, i.e., at the site of the geothermal energy facility (Brunks, 2010). Hall et al. (2015) provide additional support for this trade-off by identifying incongruences between the views of local and distant communities regarding energy facility development. Thus, we suggest that in the context of environmental protection, the distance between consumers and the energy facility potentially causing environmental damage can help explain the weak effect of EI.

Reliable and transparent communication between companies and consumers is extremely important for consumers in all BRICS countries, even though it is less important than local communities' well-being. This is in line with previous research suggesting that consumers desire more information about the impacts of companies' activities, and consider reliable and transparent CSR communication very important (Hansen et al., 2010; Vollero et al., 2016). Our findings also highlight that CSR communication has a direct and positive impact on companies' financial performances through the effect of consumer loyalty. As such, companies should very carefully manage their CSR communication strategies and activities and avoid the phenomenon of “greenwashing”, as both perceptions of greenwashing and deliberately misleading strategies can negatively affect consumers' views of the company (Dobele et al., 2014; Parguel et al., 2011), and thus damage its revenues.

Differences emerged in our findings when each country was examined separately, rather than considering all BRICS countries as a whole.

The attribute with the most effect on whether consumers are loyal or not to the company is confirmed to be ILC. A company's impact on the local community's well-being represents the key attribute for

consumers regardless of the country considered, so the generalizability of this finding across developing countries that share similar socio-economic characteristics with BRICS can be ensured. Conversely, consumers do not take into consideration managers' multiculturalism in their decision to be loyal or not to the company, so employing foreign or local managers is not a matter of evaluation. This reinforces those researches that show consumers as caring less about working conditions and, in particular, about integration and/or ethnic origin (Carrigan & Attalia, 2001; Brunks, 2010). Although companies could concentrate their attention on ILC instead of MN for CSR activities within the SD, the significance of MN in the case of all BRICS countries demonstrates that this attribute is not completely overlooked by consumers, and companies should carefully consider their employment of managers. In agreement with the results in the case of all BRICS, the mental categorization of consumers on what happens locally and far away may account for EI non-significance. China is the exception, with EI significant and stronger than CUT. When evaluating CSR activities, Chinese consumers may prefer to focus on achieved results instead of companies' motives (Kim & Ji, 2017), which are the basis of CSR communications alongside descriptions of CSR activities, thus leading to this inversion of importance between CUT and EI. However, "Chinese companies have been much less active in communicating CSR with their stakeholders" (Kim & Ji, 2017), and consider the disclosures of social and environmental information as a mere compliance duty (Kim & Ji, 2017). The joint effect of the tendency for consumers to focus on results instead of motives and companies' poor CSR communication may be that consumers prioritize EI (impact-oriented) over CUT (motives-oriented) in their decision to be loyal to the company. Lastly, the leading role played by China in addressing environmental pollution (mainly from its industrial processes) may also result in Chinese consumers being more sensitive to environmental issues compared with the other countries in the study, leading them to prefer EI over CUT in terms of importance.

For Brazil, Russia and South Africa, similar conclusions can be drawn as in the case of all BRICS countries when referring to CUT, in that reliable and transparent CSR communication is considered to be of high importance (Hansen et al., 2010; Vollero et al., 2016) and to have a direct and positive impact on companies' financial performance. Despite its importance in such countries, CUT is not significant for India. In addition, India is the only country in which MN, EI and CUT are simultaneously not significant, and shows the lowest ILC strength compared with the other countries. Possible explanations could be the following. Indian consumers are highly price sensitive, place little value on CSR activities, and are typically unwilling to pay a premium price for the products and/or services of socially responsible companies (Pradhan, 2018). In addition, Indian companies do not prioritize CSR activities, with only 17% having a stated CSR policy, and India has no officially recognized guidelines for reporting these activities (Amaladoss et al., 2013). Culturally, in India doing good discreetly is more desirable than doing good for publicity, and this cultural peculiarity also affects CSR communication, which is usually structured in a top-down approach without the participation of employees and other stakeholders (Amaladoss et al., 2013). Thus, Indian consumers identified ILC as the only attribute worthy of evaluation, leaving the company with much room for manoeuvre in its CSR activities.

6. Conclusions

The aim of this study is to empirically test the CSR domains that are valued by consumers, and the relative importance they give to each CSR domain when evaluating their loyalty towards a company, taking into account different cultural environments. We used the rologit model, which is a vignette-

base method, to test our hypotheses, using a geothermal energy facility development as the setting for our study. From the analyses of our vignettes, the following conclusions can be drawn.

The two attributes of SD show very different impacts on consumer loyalty. From a strategic perspective, companies should prioritize the understanding of how and to what extent their business actions (e.g. development of energy facilities) impact local communities' well-being over the employment of managers with multicultural backgrounds. This finding is extremely valuable for multinational companies involved in the construction of facilities, as it can enable standardization. When operating within countries such as BRICS, multinational companies can adopt standardized external processes when involving local communities, in addition to standardized internal processes for achieving such involvement. External processes can include the standardization of a methodology for gathering data from local communities (e.g., questionnaires or interviews), and methods of interaction (e.g. seminars, focus groups, etc.), in order to account for local communities when addressing the impacts of company's actions or facilities on the neighbouring social environment. Internal processes, instead, include those required to enable a dialogue with local communities, such as the standardization of procedures within departments and of human resources selection procedures. Although a considerable level of standardization is potentially achievable, context-specific characteristics will remain. Thus, multinational companies should ensure they avoid the "department store" approach in their CSR strategies and activities, and adapt them to context-specific factors (e.g. socio-cultural characteristics, local communities' needs, etc.) (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2019). In the case of MN, companies could be tempted to solely employ local managers, or to solely consider ILC for CSR activities within the SD. Such drastic measures should be avoided, since the importance consumers assign to the integration of people and ethnic origins in the workplace has been noted (Crowe & Simon, 2000; Brunks, 2010), and studies have also highlighted how companies that embrace integration and employ managers from multicultural backgrounds perform better in terms of CSR (Ballesteros et al., 2015). These issues should be considered by companies when considering MN, and additional research is required to establish the causes of MN weakness and significance variability, through considering other developing countries and sectors.

In terms of CSR activities within the ED, companies should consider the trade-off resulting from consumers' prioritization of attributes. Environmental pollution can be a potential direct cause of poor health in local communities, even though consumers rated it as of low importance in terms of their loyalty to the company. This trade-off may tempt companies to focus their attention on guaranteeing consumer loyalty by prioritizing CSR activities within the SD and the CD instead of within the ED. However, ED-based CSR activities still have strategic value for the analysed companies. In fact, such activities can indirectly contribute to consumer loyalty through two different ways. First, CSR activities aimed at protecting the environment around the operation site can ensure local communities' well-being, which positively influences consumer loyalty. Second, these activities can strengthen communication, which has been identified as the second most important attribute for consumer loyalty. Consequently, companies' ED-based CSR remain favourable strategic and operational activities, regardless of the importance given by consumers.

In terms of CD-based CSR activities, companies should ensure reliable and transparent CSR communication to positively affect consumer loyalty. Moreover, companies can develop a standardized modus operandi through which they can communicate their CSR activities. The process of standardization could also be applied in countries with similar socio-economic characteristics, and

it refers to both corporate communication instruments (e.g. CSR reports and, ethical codes), and to marketing communication instruments (e.g. advertising and sponsoring). However, the process of standardization refers to the way in which companies communicate their CSR efforts, i.e., the instruments, rather than the contents. Thus, companies should differentiate the contents of their CSR communication according to the peculiarities of the country in which they are operating. Consequently, companies' CD-based CSR activities should emphasize the transparency and reliability of the content communicated, and ensure continued communication with established ad-hoc content.

Our findings also have implications for managers. By focusing on the leverage typically used to increase the customer base, i.e., reducing prices and improving customer care, energy companies may overlook important strategic aspects. To avoid this, they should i) assess the CSR domains and attributes that consumers value the most, according to the country where the business action or facility is implemented; ii) prioritize their CSR investments according to the assessment, adjusting for potential trade-offs such as that within the ED; and iii) identify communications strategies that can convey in a transparent and reliable way consumer demands.

This study has some limitations. First, we cannot ensure that consumers strictly followed the "repeated best-worst" process in evaluating the six vignettes, and if they did not, they may have experienced additional difficulties in expressing their preferences, potentially increasing the risk of random answers. Future studies should take this into account and use more sophisticated IT techniques to ensure the use of the "repeated best-worst" process. Second, we chose attributes and modalities of attributes that are not univocal, even though we limited our discretion by relying on the literature and on two different pre-tests. Future studies should consider other attributes and modalities of variation to gain more insights about consumers' reactions to companies' CSR activities. Third, the CVVV method only allows to extract the relative value given to each attribute by each respondent and it does not allow to extract the absolute value as the factorial survey method is able to do. Future studies could use the factorial survey method to elicit the absolute value given to each attribute by each respondent. However, they must also consider that absurd vignettes may be generated and discriminating among random and non-random answers is impossible in the factorial survey method. Lastly, the rologit should be applied in other service contexts and in other developing countries, and conducted with local communities' respondents, thus either confirming or contradicting the findings.

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Tables

Table 1. Attributes, modalities of variation and associated weights

Attribute/Step	Modalities of variation of each attribute	Weight
Impact on local communities (ILC)	The well-being of the local community is higher because of the presence of the company	3
	The company does not generate positive or negative impacts for the local community	2
	The company negatively impacts the well-being of the local community	1
Managers nationality (MN)	The company ensures a balance between employing (nationality) managers and foreign managers	3
	Only a minority of the managers employed by the company are from foreign countries	2
	The company employs only (nationality) managers	1
Environmental impact (EI)	The company has no negative impact on the natural environment	3
	The company has a limited, but not permanent, negative impact on the natural environment	2
	The company has a highly negative and permanent impact on the natural environment	1
Communication transparency (CUT)	The company provides transparent and reliable information to customers about its activities	3
	The company provides only partial information to customers about its activities	2
	The company does not provide information to customers about its activities	1

Table 2. Hypotheses with the hypothesized paths and signs

Hypotheses	Domains	Hypothesised path	Hypothesised sign
H1a	SD	ILC → Cons. Loy.	+
		MN → Cons. Loy.	+
H1b	ED	EI → Cons. Loy.	+
H1c	CD	CUT → Cons. Loy.	+
H2	/	ED > SD > CD	/

Table 3. Coefficients and level of significance for each attribute detailed for all BRICS [*p<0.05 e **p<0.01]

Countries	Attributes			
	ILC	MN	EI	CUT
BRICS	.4806477**	-.0562572*	.0837864**	.2425634**

Table 4. Coefficients and level of significance for each attribute detailed for each country [*p<0.05 e **p<0.01]

Countries	Attributes			
	ILC	MN	EI	CUT
Brazil	.4839619**	-.0690771	.0379106	.2997329**
Russia	.6811824**	-.0829496	.0980183	.3686322**
India	.2182059**	.0124115	.059231	.060384
China	.441597**	-.0733204	.2123668**	.1655273*
South Africa	.5836309**	-.0606806	.0270758	.3160659**